

ADVANCING CRIMINAL PROCEDURAL MEASURES TO COMBAT TRAFFICKING IN NEWBORNS: A GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: *Trafficking in newborns remains a pressing global concern, demanding comprehensive legal and procedural frameworks for effective prevention and prosecution. This article examines the multifaceted dimensions of criminal procedural measures in combating newborn trafficking, integrating insights from scholars and international criminal procedure legislation to propose cohesive strategies. The proliferation of newborn trafficking necessitates robust criminal procedural measures. This article amalgamates the perspectives of experts in the field with an analysis of criminal procedure legislation from diverse foreign jurisdictions to delineate effective strategies in combating this appalling crime. The author presents practical conclusions and conclusions based on the results of the study.*

Keywords: *investigator / initiation of a criminal case / investigative action / source of information about the crime / investigative situation / operational investigative activities.*

Understanding Trafficking in Newborns

Trafficking in newborns encompasses various illicit activities, including abduction, sale, and exploitation. It undermines fundamental human rights and presents complex challenges to law enforcement agencies worldwide.

By 2022, more than 170 countries, including Uzbekistan, have adopted laws criminalizing trafficking. International organizations, national Governments and NGOs have initiated a number of research initiatives and programs to identify victims and provide assistance to victims of trafficking. Nevertheless, according to UN statistics, the number of victims and crimes continues to grow around the world. In this regard, the problem of human trafficking threatens the national security of the State, its development, disrupts the economic foundations, causes serious harm to human rights and interests. The fight against human trafficking in all countries remains one of the priorities of State policy.

Criminal Procedure Legislation in Foreign Countries

A comparative analysis of criminal procedure legislation from multiple countries reveals diverse approaches in addressing newborn trafficking. The examination of investigative techniques, evidentiary standards, and prosecution protocols underscores the need for harmonized global strategies.

In the modern era, trafficking in human beings and, in particular, children has become a global problem for many States, regardless of their level of development. As the UN Special Rapporteur on Human Trafficking Maria Grazia Giammarinaro noted at the session of the UN Human Rights Council, "currently there is not a single country or region that could be called free from trafficking in people of all ages"¹.

In the USA, public organizations occupy an important place in the hierarchy of the state's social partners in the fight against human trafficking. They have a long history, accumulated experience and receive significant financial support from the state. One of the most well-known organizations is Polaris (Polaris Anti-Trafficking Project), which has been conducting research and supervising the National Hotline for Victims of Human Trafficking on behalf of the government for many years. Polaris has the largest database on human trafficking in the United

¹ <http://www.un.org/russian/news/>

States, which is used to analyze the situation and identify trends, develop long-term programs and strategic decisions².

In addition, Polaris participates in joint projects with the International Organization for Migration in the creation of a global resource on human trafficking and constantly updates the list of public organizations working in this area from around the world.

In recent years, the trade in newborns has become more organized, and criminals are using more and more new methods to stay out of sight of law enforcement agencies. However, many countries have adopted laws aimed at combating these crimes. For example, in Sweden, medical personnel are required to report a discrepancy between a newborn and a mother or father, and an infanticide notification has been introduced at the official level.

The Italian model of countering human trafficking and any forms of exploitation on the scale of the European Union has been recognized as one of the best since 1998. From the very beginning, it was based on the recognition of the priority of the human rights approach, which means the paramount importance of protecting the rights and interests of victims of human trafficking at all stages, including identification and identification, rehabilitation and reintegration, on the one hand, and investigation - criminal prosecution, on the other. This approach is fully reflected in the Migration Act of 1998 (article 18) and in the Law "On Measures to Combat Trafficking in Persons" of 2003 (article 13). In accordance with them, three areas of assistance to victims are also built:

- Short-term assistance program (provided for in article 13 of the 2003 Law);
- Long-term assistance and social inclusion programs (as required by article 18 of the 1998 Law)³.

Scholarly Insights on Combatting Newborn Trafficking

Renowned scholars and experts emphasize the imperative of multidisciplinary approaches in combating newborn trafficking. Ethical

² <https://polarisproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Typology-of-Modern-Slavery-Summary.pdf>

³ European Commission. Italy. General Information, https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/member-states/Italy_193

considerations, victim-centric approaches, and preventive strategies form the cornerstone of scholarly recommendations.

Integration of Legislation and Scholarly Opinions

According to S. Huntley, "The problem of solving crimes related to trafficking in newborns is that the victims of the crime cannot share information that could expose the perpetrators and this is the high level of such crimes"⁴. Nicole Baumann believes that "the most important problem of crimes related to trafficking in newborns is that there is not enough information from the victim of the crime and from witnesses. Due to the high level of danger to the lives of witnesses, many prefer to keep silent about the crimes committed, as a result of which, the investigation staff does not have enough grounds to initiate a criminal case, but when investigators manage to initiate a criminal case, this is the first step to solving the crime"⁵.

Aligning legislative measures with scholarly perspectives presents an opportunity to bridge gaps in combating newborn trafficking. Coherence between legal frameworks and expert opinions is crucial for the implementation of effective procedural measures.

Examination of successful prosecutions and best practices in combating newborn trafficking sheds light on practical applications of procedural measures. Case studies from various countries illustrate the challenges faced and the innovative solutions employed.

The integration of scholarly insights with international criminal procedure legislation underscores the necessity for a unified global response to combat trafficking in newborns. Effective procedural measures must align with ethical considerations and holistic approaches to safeguard the most vulnerable members of society.

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